

EMBODIED LAUDATO SI' SPIRITUALITY: A TRANSFORMATIVE PATHWAY IN ORGANIZATIONAL ECOLOGICAL PRACTICES

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ABSTRACT

This study investigates Embodied Laudato Si' Spirituality as a transformative approach in organizational ecological projects. This paper explores the potential of spirituality, as articulated in Pope Francis' encyclical Laudato Si', to transcend personal devotion and cultivate ecological awareness, organizational culture, and social involvement. The research utilized a qualitative case study method to elucidate the influence of faith-based principles on the formulation of sustainable policies and practices that encompass ethical, ecological, and spiritual dimensions. The findings suggest that embodied spirituality promotes comprehensive development by integrating reflection with environmental involvement. The findings also inferred that caring for the environment is both a spiritual duty and something we all need to do to protect our shared earth. The study demonstrates that Laudato Si' spirituality is a moral and practical means for organizations to raise awareness about the environment and create substantial changes.

Keywords: *Laudato Si', Spirituality, Ecological Projects, Transformation*

INTRODUCTION

A worldwide concern is the need to "care for our common home." Since the ecological issue is currently everyone's responsibility, Pope Francis, as leader of the Universal Catholic Church, addresses this inclusively to all peoples worldwide. The term "all of these people" (Pope Francis, 2015) would refer to all individuals, including children,

youth, and people with disabilities, as well as all non-governmental and industrial organizations, communities, and groups, including those that are political or religious. They are all involved in the situation regarding the expanding environmental issue and the cooperation in finding answers, healing, and reparations.

Concrete involvement in the revitalization of ideas, attitudes, and behaviors regarding our ecosystem is called for in both Pope Francis' 2015 encyclical, "Laudato Si'," and the endorsement by United Nations member states of the 2030 Agenda for Sustainable Development (United Nations, 2025). Individually, at home, and even at their respective workplaces, these changes may impact every facet of people's lives and activities. This is the primary focus of an investigation of the operations and procedures of an organization. We are currently confronted with the question of how far we have come in achieving the Sustainable Development Goals. Even though the 2030 plan is only a few years old, how much is known about the various sectors' efforts? What exceptional contributions do they make, and how big an impact can they have on others to follow suit?

This study examined the role those commercial organizations—more especially, the well-known Metro Manila Coffee Shops—have had in addressing the climate crisis. Nowadays, a wide range of age groups frequent cafes or coffee shops for personal, professional, and leisure purposes. This implies that wherever individuals go, their consumption and the effects are also present: Waste, Product, and Consumption. Here, the views and behaviors of business organizations can be identified, particularly their involvement in addressing the environmental catastrophe. According to the latest statistics, at least 500 billion disposable cups are used annually worldwide (Osbourne, 2023). Eighty percent of Filipinos drink an average of 2.5 cups of coffee per day, making the country the second-largest coffee consumer in Asia (Luna, 2024). Consider how these cafes would dispose of only one waste item each day. "A large chain coffee shop can sell an astounding 700 cups of coffee per day," according to Osbourne. In this instance, one could consider their waste management technique. How specifically do they contribute to the resolution of climate change?

Could it be that they, both individually and collectively, also respond to embody the spirituality of Laudato Si'? The well-known coffee shops in the Metro area are the subject of an investigation into their beliefs, methods, and Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) initiatives, which address the United Nations' Sustainable Development Goals and Pope Francis' objectives outlined in Laudato Si'. They may have a strong understanding of corporate social responsibility, but how much do they actually contribute to environmental preservation efforts? A handbook or set of guidelines on corporate or organizational ecological spirituality might be formed with their individual contributions. They might also serve as a way to educate their clients, which will lead to a series of reactions. According to Matthew Fox's (1991) Four Paths to Creation Spirituality, this might be their Via Transformativa, a route of transformation that involves new ideas, attitudes, and behaviors. With God's help, they may then be able to embrace the spirituality of Laudato Si' and make a lifelong commitment to genuine care for our shared home. Hence, this

study investigated the role of commercial organizations—particularly the well-known coffee shops in Metro Manila—in addressing ecological issues.

Research Questions

The researchers provided an answer to the pertinent issue of how business organizations, specifically coffee shops, respond to the call to address the climate crisis.

In particular, this study wanted to know the answers to these questions:

1. What are the participants' shared experiences, attitudes, and practices on the Subject of Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) in relation to environmental conservation?
2. What actions do business coffee shops in Metro Manila take in response to the Climate Change Resolution?
3. What are the implications of the study's findings in the teaching of spirituality?

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

This study used the qualitative case study method in conjunction with the narrative research strategy to gain a comprehensive understanding of the life sharing of members of business organizations, specifically popular cafes or coffee shops in Metro Manila. The selected methodology enabled the researchers to gain a comprehensive understanding of a complex phenomenon within the study's natural setting (An End-to-End Dissertation Consulting Firm, 2024).

Sources of Data

The information used in this study was obtained from the managers or employees of the Cafes or coffee shops in question, who shared their ideas, practices, and experiences. Additional requisite data was obtained from website information (archival records), direct observation, and tangible manifestations. Kurt Schoch wrote about this in his 2020 article "Case Study Approach."

The researchers interviewed five (5) businesses (Cafes) in the Metro area, including Starbucks, Figaro Cafe, The Coffee Bean and Tea Leaf, and Ueshima Coffee Company (UCC). They were purposively picked. The members of these organizations were able to engage in in-depth conversations about how they expect to respond, drawing on their own practices and experiences.

To get the necessary information for this study, the researchers conducted in-depth survey interviews with a limited number of participants due to scheduling,

availability, and cooperation issues. Each participant was given enough time to share his answers or experiences related to the four paths of creation spirituality.

For the individual interview, the participants were asked these questions:

1. What does the organization think about the environment or creation?
2. What does the organization do to make the ecological issue worse?
3. What does the group do to help the environment or make the problem with the environment less severe?
4. What can the organization do to help solve climate crises?

Data Collection and Analysis

Guided by a list of criteria for research participants, the researchers sought assistance from the administrative offices to identify potential participants for the study. After identifying prospective participants for this study, they were subjected to an individual, personally recorded survey interview. In cases where the data supplied was ambiguous, the researchers validated it by explaining it to them personally or over the phone. The recordings were then converted into understandable written form and used for analysis.

The research employed a qualitative case study approach. The acquired data were examined repeatedly to ensure appropriate coding during the analysis stage. This is emphasized in Schoch's (2020) paper on the Case Study Approach. According to him, the analysis is divided into numerous sections, including descriptions of the studies, as well as details on who, what, where, and when. Interpreting covers the initial stage of coding, which involves analyzing the data, concluding, and assessing significance.

RESULTS

1. Participants' Personal Experiences, Attitudes, and Practices on the Subject of Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) in Relation to Environmental Conservation

Table 1: The Via Positiva Cases

<ul style="list-style-type: none">• We are more than just a coffee company, but a people company.
<ul style="list-style-type: none">• We live by our saying that when we take care of people, we take care of the planet.
<ul style="list-style-type: none">• We want to inspire more Filipinos to live sustainably even in their own small ways.
<ul style="list-style-type: none">• We are set out to be a different kind of company, guided by a belief that the pursuit of profit is not in conflict with the pursuit of doing good.
<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Our work goes far beyond making a great cup of coffee, but we aim to uplift the lives of those who connect with us, one person, one cup, and one neighborhood at a time.

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- We continuously thrive on finding ways to promote love for the environment to our community through various efforts.
 - Policy goals are embedded and remain our core in everything we do in business. We believe we have a responsibility to minimize the energy, carbon, water and waste impacts of our business and recognize that these impacts occur not just in the daily operations of our portfolio but also through our entire value chain.
 - A successful, sustainable business depends on a healthy planet. That is why we have an ambition to help nature thrive.
 - We go the distance to protect the well-being of our ecosystems so that we can continue to produce coffee with sustainability in mind.
 - We stand by what we believe in - to honor the Filipino weaving customs that our forefathers passed down to us. They pay homage to the past by preserving our culture via the use of our exquisite weaves today. They held the view that each fiber links us as a single community and a single people. The national tapestries of our country are full of symbolic meaning that depicts our traditions and identity.
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Table 1 depicts organizations' grasp of ecological concerns. They emphasize that creation is significant and must be prioritized over other things. They think that "taking care of people is also taking care of the planet." Analyzing the data, these understandings can be classified into the key values of Maka-Diyos, Maka-Tao, Maka-Bayan, and Maka-Kalikasan, which serve as the guiding principles for the Filipino curriculum, implemented beginning with basic education. These essential principles, which every educated Filipino understands, are at the heart of every initiative undertaken, whether in a for-profit or non-profit enterprise.

Table 2. The Via Negativa Cases

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- Plastic wastes from used coffee capsules, disposable utensils, straws and cups.
 - The use of bubble wrap in packaging.
 - The use of plastic waste that ends up in our city's landfills and seas.
 - The energy, carbon, (electricity and air-conditioning system) water and waste impacts of our business and recognize that these impacts occur not just in the daily operations of our portfolio but also through our entire value chain.
 - The time consumed in coffee shops instead of with family members.
 - The coffee shops as modern-day venue for unproductivity, gossips, etc,
 - The concern on profit alone.
 - The lack of Transparency of strategies to customers.
 - The lack of orientation of policies to all employees.
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Table 2 illustrates that coffee shop groups are aware of the environmental dangers associated with their trash and how some people perceive it. The vast majority of paper and plastic waste generated daily by both large and small coffee shop chains contributes to the elements that influence the ecological disaster. Using the Via Negativa in Creation Spirituality, each person in the group must undergo the dark awareness of how his actions have harmed others. If not, then it is a denial of that reality, to say the least. Indeed, they are aware of the types of waste that coffee shops generate.

2. Actions Taken by Business Coffee Shops in Metro Manila in Response to Climate Change Resolution

Table 3: Metro Manila Business Coffee Shops Actions in Response to Climate Change Resolution

<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Our customers can enjoy 10 Php off on every handcrafted drink that they order.
<ul style="list-style-type: none">• In 2021, we are excited to launch BREW A CUP, BUILD A FUTURE, our capsule recycling program.
<ul style="list-style-type: none">• In all stores and through delivery, we shifted to using 100% paper straws to bring the experience to our customers wherever they may be.
<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Since April 2021, we've successfully replaced all fillers of delivery packages ordered through our official e-commerce flagship store on Lazada. To help reduce plastic waste, we shifted from bubble wrap to carton box and carton filters.
<ul style="list-style-type: none">• We encourage our customers to be involved in making eco-friendly decisions when they visit any of our stores. We've resumed sale of reusable cups in our stores to help reduce plastic waste the use of "for-here-ware" for dine-in customers, and allowing customers to safely use their own mugs and tumblers again through a contactless approach.
<ul style="list-style-type: none">• We've partnered with Envirotech Waste Recycling Inc., an innovative local company that transforms assorted plastics into durable furniture or functional construction materials to reduce the amount of plastic waste that ends up in our city's landfills and seas.
<ul style="list-style-type: none">• We have partnered with Philippine Parks and Biodiversity in launching a new product that aims to not only promote sustainability but also reforestation and community empowerment.
<ul style="list-style-type: none">• With every purchase of the 'Tomorrow' tumbler, we will be adopting a tree under the Program of Eco Explorations and Philippine Parks and Biodiversity. One 'Tomorrow' tumbler can contribute to these efforts: (1) Maintain and nurture seedlings to be used for the reforestation program & (2) Support and empower Forest Rangers who are in charge of restoring and protecting the reforestation site.
<ul style="list-style-type: none">• Our chosen reforestation site is Mt. Balagbag, Ipo Watershed. The project site is located inside Ipo Watershed, a watershed reservation in Norzagaray and San Jose del Monte, Bulacan and partly in Rodriguez, Rizal. This watershed is part of the large system which includes Umiray, Angat and La Mesa that supplies water to 98% of Metro Manila. One of the mountains part of the watershed is Mount Balagbag which is the reforestation site of Eco Explorations and Philippine Parks and Biodiversity.
<ul style="list-style-type: none">• We also encourage people to think about the UN's Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs) through initiatives such as online seminars and the development of coffee products that harness the beverage's inherent functional health benefits. We work to foster better lives for all through coffee.
<ul style="list-style-type: none">• As part of its ongoing commitment to empowering communities, our company has initiated the "Brewing Opportunities" program, which aims to equip local

coffee farmers with knowledge, tools, and resources to improve their coffee cultivation practices. Through this program, our company continues to foster long-term relationships with coffee growers, ensuring fair and sustainable practices that benefit the entire value chain.

- Before 2018 ended, we ran a fundraising campaign to provide solar lights for families living without electricity in the remote mountain community of Laginan, Sarangani province.
- Through the generosity of our customers who supported our campaign, we were able to raise over PHP 2M worth of donations. This enabled us to install solar energy systems to 68 homes and 2 teachers' quarters through our partnership with Stiftung Solarenergie Foundation.
- The company participates in tree-planting program. Segregating of trash is also a practice of our company. We use eco-friendly paper cups for hot drinks, brown tissue, paper or fiber straws, and paper bags for packaging.
- Fund-raising campaign in Batangas, "from crop to cup." Giving opportunities for communities to plant coffee.
- Coffee ground wastes are given for free to customers for planting and other purposes.

Table 3 highlights each coffee shop's role in addressing the challenges of single-use plastic that harm our environment. They have devised innovative methods for reducing plastic waste and developing campaigns that will benefit consumers and many industries. They use a range of green programs to help mitigate the climate crisis.

3. Study's Findings Implications for the Teaching of Spirituality

The study's final objective was to address the question: What are the implications of the study's findings in the teaching of spirituality? An assessment of the chosen coffee cafes in Metro Manila led to the conclusion that spirituality is not solely an internal or personal and educational experience, but is also manifested in the ways communities, businesses, and organizations nurture it.

DISCUSSION

Participants' Personal Experiences, Attitudes, and Practices on the Subject of Corporate Social Responsibility (CSR) in Relation to Environmental Conservation

The Via Positiva Cases

The Via Ad Deum Organizational Leadership (VAD-OL). Via Ad Deum (The Path to God), Organizational Leadership (Maka-Diyos) is a God-centered approach to leadership in organizations. All human actions must be centered on global virtues and ideals derived from scripture and religious beliefs. Nature is God's gift to mankind, which we must conserve and cultivate. Nobody has sole ownership of the lands supplied for every being born; only stewardship. We are stewards of nature's gifts, utilizing them for

the benefit of everybody. Indeed, the coffee industry continues to operate while remaining cognizant of its environmental impact. They believe that successful and sustainable business practices depend on a healthy planet; therefore, prioritizing environmental welfare over profit is not only an obligation but also a task, a duty, and a moral necessity, as it positively impacts a business's operations. This pattern of results is consistent with Roffé's (2023) stance that sustainable practices benefit companies financially.

The Via Ad Alios Organizational Leadership (VAA-OL). The Via Ad Alios (The Path of Others) Organizational Leadership is defined as other-centered leadership in organizations (Maka-Tao). This type of business leadership is aware of its responsibilities to others. First and foremost, the primary purpose is to serve; profit is secondary. Income is thus the product of that other-centeredness, which stems from the organization's selflessness in prioritizing the consumer. The consumer will choose a business not just based on the quality of its products, but also on the quality of its services. "We are more than just a coffee company, but a people company," they tell me. "We live by our saying that when we take care of people, we take care of the planet," and "We want to inspire more Filipinos to live sustainably even in their own small way," are conscious of their goals, which include establishing a business and committing to providing the best possible service to their customers.

The Via Patriam Nostram Organizational Leadership (VPN-OL). Via Patriam Nostram (The Path to Our Country) Organizational Leadership is defined as leadership in an organization that demonstrates love for the country (Maka-Bayan). Every organization expects its efforts to contribute to the development of a society or nation. Every organization's investment aims to improve the lives of people in the community or society by generating money and contributing to progress. As stated by one of the participants, "Our work goes far beyond making a great cup of coffee, but we aim to uplift the lives of those who connect with us, one person, one cup, and one neighborhood at a time." Every endeavor speaks to more than just a great cup of coffee, as it aims to become an integral part of Filipino culture — the taste that suits every Filipino's palate, the tradition of unity in good times and bad, and the family-orientedness and togetherness that is often shared over a cup of coffee. Other coffee shop owners advocate for communities to develop their own business abilities.

"We stand by what we believe in - to honor the Filipino weaving customs that our forefathers passed down to us. They pay homage to the past by preserving our culture via the use of our exquisite weaves today. They held the view that each fiber links us as a single community and a single people. The national tapestries of our country are full of symbolic meaning that depict our traditions and identity."

The Via Ad Naturam Organizational Leadership (VAN-OL). The Via Ad Naturam (The Path to Nature) Organization is a group that promotes love for nature (Maka-Kalikasan) and leads other groups. People, and even more so organizations, can be held liable for the trash that is harming the environment. As a duty that comes with the right to invest, we all need to work together to safeguard the environment by devising ways to save the world, which is our shared home. The Vision and Mission of any firm serve as a

way to promote goodness, such as protecting the environment. For example, "We are set out to be a different kind of company, guided by a belief that the pursuit of profit is not in conflict with the pursuit of doing good." The desire to acquire must go hand in hand with the desire to serve with goodness. When done correctly, these activities will become a part of everyone who works for or is a member of an organization. The group will train its members, all the way down to the customers, and this will be a chain of eco-friendly actions. "Policy goals are built into everything we do in business and are at the heart of what we do. We believe it is our duty to minimize the impact of our business on energy, carbon, water, and waste. We recognize that these effects occur not only in the daily operations of our portfolio but also throughout our entire value chain. The coffee and plastic garbage are not the only things that will be taken care of; the energy, carbon, and water used in running the whole business will also be. As mentioned by one of the participants, "We go the extra mile to protect the health of our ecosystems so that we can keep making coffee in a way that is good for the environment." So, this must be the goal: stability and sustainability in business. We go through nature, we speak with it, and we work for it. These findings reinforce Kollmus & Agyeman's (2002) investigation into the reasons behind individuals' "green" behavior, highlighting that a sense of duty and moral obligation significantly drives sustainable acts.

The Via Negativa Cases

The Material Waste. Used coffee capsules, disposable cutlery, straws, and plastic cups for to-go cold drinks, as well as plastic bubble wrap for delivery product packaging, are all examples of material waste. These waste materials wind up in our city's landfills and seas. Consumers who place to-go orders often leave their waste on sidewalks or ledges outside restaurants, delegating the responsibility for trash disposal to community cleaners.

The Energy Waste. Energy waste refers to the wasteful use of energy in homes and businesses. The energy wasted from power on air-conditioning systems and appliances, such as microwave ovens, toasters, coffee makers, blenders, and others, which are used during the business's everyday operations. The constant whirring sound of machinery and electronics plugged in throughout the day, as well as in 24-hour coffee shops, indicates the accumulation of energy use, which leads to greenhouse gas emissions.

The Service-Orientedness Waste. This refers to an inefficient technique of implementing corporate policies and procedures. It occurs when appropriate and effective service is not provided at a commercial facility. Customer satisfaction cannot be achieved until the organization's aims and beliefs are adequately communicated to all members. The failure to properly train all members, from managers to regular employees, on practices, rules, and strategies is a loss of time spent developing policies and principles. The lack of awareness of various regulations and promotional methods among individuals on company sites demonstrates a lack of cooperation between top management and their staff. Crafting those rules and strategies without adequately orienting frontline workers may result in a trend-following practice. Every member of the frontline must undergo

complete orientation and training; otherwise, it will appear to be based solely on concepts rather than actual practice. This allows them to strictly enforce the policies while also thoroughly explaining the reasons behind them to the clients. As a result, customers may learn and grasp their position as universe children. The evidence supports the claim by Liu et al. (2023) that understanding corporate policies and environmental responsibility (CER) has a significant positive impact on business performance. Hence, a better understanding of ecological stewardship.

The Cultural Waste. It refers to a community's decrease in its positive cultural practices. Cultural waste occurs in coffee shops when consumers are insensitive to their actions while consuming products both inside and outside the establishment. Even though segregated garbage bins are provided inside the coffee shop, many people continue to disregard the "Clean as You Go" guideline. Customers continue to favor disposable cups in 'dine-in' or 'for here' food goods over reusable ones, demonstrating the throw-away culture. Friends and families, especially small children, often choose to stay up late in coffee shops to enjoy the food and ambiance of a cool setting, rather than staying at home, which suggests a decline in the quality of life in Filipino households. Worse, coffee shops have become a modern gathering place for gossip, allowing them to spend more time together at the expense of small children who must be put to bed on time.

The key findings of the study provide supporting evidence that business executives must avoid the following habits that may contribute to increased waste, including their financial investment:

Organizational Nonchalance. An organization is a dynamic entity capable of keeping up with trends and being proactive in the application of laws and policies. It must utilize all available resources to include a holistic approach to business processes in its vision and goals. Religious words or orientations based on a model or framework can aid in the development of attainable goals and missions. A good business thrives when it actively pursues customer pleasure in all forms.

Organizational Individualism. While every firm strives to distinguish itself from the competition, it cannot thrive without partnerships and collaborations. Universal calls for new trends and practices are tailored to ensure that customers' needs are addressed. It is good competition while also avoiding bandwagons. An organization, no matter how small, can devise strategies for how its business can contribute to addressing the climate crisis. Other organizations may be seeking the exact cause and believe that partnership or collaboration is more effective.

Profit-oriented Leadership. While the company's purpose is to maintain revenue, corporate social responsibility must be upheld at all times. Every firm has the opportunity to increase productivity and profit, but with that opportunity comes responsibility. These key results support the findings of Wright & Nyberg (2024) that corporations are major greenhouse gas polluters, yet they are also depicted as significant players in climate change mitigation.

Actions Taken by Business Coffee Shops in Metro Manila in Response to the Climate Change Resolution

Customer-Empowered Green Program

This plan or program can encourage customers to reduce their use of single-use plastics by requiring them to carry their own containers for drinks every time they make a purchase. If you bring your own cups to a coffee shop, they will give you 10p off every drink you buy. *"We want our customers to make eco-friendly choices when they shop at any of our stores."* "To help reduce plastic waste, we are once again offering reusable cups for sale in our stores." "We are also allowing customers to safely use their own mugs and tumblers again, without having to touch them."

This plan is an indirect way to encourage customers to use less plastic. It makes individuals aware that there are easy things they can do in every part of their lives to help the environment. Offering free coffee grounds in coffee shops is a simple technique to get people to garden by using them as compost or fertilizer. This is an innovative initiative designed to raise awareness and encourage action on the call to help address the ecological catastrophe.

Community-Driven Green Program

The executives of the coffee shop company use communities to spread their support for the green initiative. They get their coffee from their own farms and land. For example, the "From Crop to Cup" fund-raising effort gives communities a chance to cultivate coffee. Other coffee businesses have started programs to "give local coffee farmers the knowledge, tools, and resources they need to improve how they grow coffee." This provides farmers in the area with the opportunity to acquire new skills or enhance their existing ones, ultimately benefiting them in the long run. This means that they not only share resources, but also knowledge.

A coffee firm collaborated with its consumers to give back to the community by providing them with essential items, such as solar power for their homes. Another coffee firm launched a scheme called "Tomorrow Tumbler" to raise money for tree planting. To truly be socially responsible as a business, one should not act like a philanthropist.

Collaborative-Guided Green Program

Partnerships or working together make business sectors stable, dynamic, and long-lasting. Other groups run programs or events. To cut down on the quantity of plastic garbage that ends up in our city's landfills and seas, a company worked with an "innovative local company that turns different types of plastic into sturdy furniture or useful building materials." Plastic waste does not stay waste since other organizations, which know how to turn these kinds of things into something useful, have collaborated. Projects often become a joint venture between two or more businesses. Partnerships can even occur in causes such as reforestation for the sake of the environment and empowering

people within their communities. Some of the profits are allocated to programs that support a cause.

Advocacy-Directed Green Program

Responding to Corporate social responsibility is vital for these coffee firms, as they participate in advocacy initiatives, particularly in response to the SDGs and the Climate Crisis Resolution. "We use eco-friendly paper cups for hot drinks, brown tissue, paper or fiber straws, and paper bags for packaging." Our company also practices garbage segregation. Since April 2021, we have successfully replaced all fillers in shipping packages. To assist in reducing plastic waste, we switched from bubble wrap to carton boxes and filters." These measures are fundamental steps toward mitigating the ecological problem, and when carried out diligently, can lead to changes in lifestyles, habits, and practices. Their activities, including online seminars and the development of coffee products that capitalize on the beverage's inherent health benefits, demonstrate their understanding of the Sustainable Development Goals (SDGs). We use coffee to improve people's lives." This one promotes products that can provide health benefits to customers.

A corporation had also taken part in the tree-planting effort. Providing solar lamps to residents without electricity in the remote mountain town of Laganan, Sarangani province, became one of the company's programs to address the climate problem. One innovative strategy is to sell tumblers in support of forestry and empower individuals to protect reforestation sites. Indeed, such enterprises that produce waste products daily can apply various methods to help solve our environmental problems simultaneously.

Study's Findings Implications for Teaching of Spirituality

The yielded data have some potential implications for the instruction of Spiritual and Religious courses, which should be framed as profoundly linked to ecological stewardship and social justice. Spirituality is not merely a collection of ideas or rituals; it is a living practice that manifests in organizational decisions, policies, and environmental actions. Religious teachers can emphasize that genuine spirituality requires more than just thinking about it; it involves taking action in the world. In essence, organizations that exemplify Laudato Si become models of change. This demands teaching approaches that are based on experience, facts, and an understanding of the environment, just as eco-retreats and programs that promote ecological sustainability. These outcomes align with the findings of Butarbutar et al. (2025) in their study, which indicate that incorporating ecological values into Christian Religious Education (CRE) significantly enhances students' understanding of ecological challenges and their responsibilities as stewards.

Conclusions

This research validates that Embodied Laudato Si' Spirituality serves as a transformative conduit for incorporating ecological awareness into organizational existence. By rooting ecological activities in spirituality, companies transcend mere

compliance or environmental responsibility, advancing towards a comprehensive manifestation of religion, values, and ethical dedication to the stewardship of our shared planet. The results show that spirituality, when put into practice, extends beyond personal commitment to encompass group action, workplace culture, and environmental stewardship. The study also shows that corporate ecological practices are more meaningful when they are based on a spirituality that encourages responsibility, sustainability, and connectivity. These kinds of actions create spaces where faith and action intersect, leading to communities that embody integral ecology in real, life-giving ways. Ultimately, this study reveals that Laudato Si' spirituality serves not only as a framework for ecological change but also as a spiritual guide that enables organizations to establish a new relationship with God, creation, and humanity.

Recommendations

The study's conclusions led to the following recommendations:

1. Incorporate and enhance Laudato Si' spirituality into the curricula of theology, religious education, and other spiritual disciplines to emphasize the connection between faith and ecological stewardship.
2. Organizations and institutions should keep establishing rules and programs that are based on spirituality and show how to take care of the environment.
3. The backdrop of waste management, energy conservation, and sustainable sourcing may be regarded as essential components for future investigations related to the topic.
4. Future scholars may investigate the enduring impacts of Laudato Si' Spirituality on corporate reform on a larger scale of participants.
5. Teach the front-line staff at coffee shops about their company's environmental practices so that they really care about consumers and stakeholders in all areas, not only as a way to make money or market the company.

Compliance with Ethical Standards

A letter of request was delivered to the administrator of the aforementioned business organizations, requesting an interview with either the administrator or an employee, as well as access to other resources, including records required for data collection. The identified participants were informed about the nature of this research before participating in the personal interviews. They were asked for their approval to participate in this research, which may be published. The researchers respected the respondents' right to anonymity, as expressed by their desire for data privacy. Data privacy in the report was ensured by assigning the participants a unique code that concealed their identities.

REFERENCES

An End-to-End Dissertation Consulting Firm (2024). Qualitative Case Study Methodology. Retrieved from <https://thegearconsulting.com/qualitative-case-study-methodology/>

- Butarbutar, I. et al. (2025). Integrating Environmental Ethics into Christian Religious Education: An Analytical and Interpretive Approach through Project-Based Learning. *International Journal of Education and Humanities* 5(4):698–707. Retrieved from https://www.researchgate.net/publication/396718160_Integrating_Environmental_Ethics_into_Christian_Religious_Education_An_Analytical_and_Interpretive_Approach_through_Project-Based_Learning
- Fox, M. (1991). *Creation Spirituality, Liberating Gifts for the Peoples of the Earth*. Harper San Francisco.
- Kollmus, A. & Agyeman, J. (2002). Mind the Gap: Why Do People Act Environmentally and What Are the Barriers to Pro-Environmental Behavior? *Environmental Education Research*. Vol. 8.239-260. Retrieved from https://www.researchgate.net/publication/235363126_Mind_the_Gap_Why_Do_People_Act_Environmentally_and_What_Are_the_Barriers_to_Pro-Environmental_Behavior
- Liu, R. et al. (2023). Does Corporate Environmental Responsibility Promote the Improvement of Corporate Economic Performance? – Based on the Perspective of Green Reputation. *Pol. J. Environ. Stud*. Vol. 32, No. 5 (2023), 4679–4697. Retrieved from <https://www.pjoes.com/pdf-168264-93041?filename=93041.pdf>
- Luna, J. (2024). *Urban Caffeine Fix*. Inquirer.Net. Retrieved from <https://business.inquirer.net/444007/urban-caffeine-fix>
- Osbourne, H. (2023). How Many Take-Away Coffee Cups can a Café use in a Day? *MTPak Coffee Newsletter*. Retrieved from <https://mtpak.coffee/2023/08/takeaway-coffee-cups-how-cafes-used-a-day/>
#:~:text=According%20to%20the%20National%20Coffee,cups%20of%20coffee%20per%20day.
- Pope Francis (2015). *Laudato Si, Encyclical Letter*. Libreria Editrice Vaticana, Vatican City.
- Roffé, M.A. (2023). The impact of sustainable practices on the financial performance of companies: A review of the literature. Retrieved from <https://www.redalyc.org/journal/3579/357976095012/357976095012.pdf>
- Schoch, K. (2020). *Case Study Research*. Sage Publications, Inc. Accessed from https://uk.sagepub.com/sites/default/files/upm-assets/105275_book_item_105275.pdf
- United Nations. (2025). *Asia and the Pacific SDG Progress Report 2025*. ISBN: 9789210034739. United Nations Publications. Retrieved from <https://repository.unescap.org/bitstream/handle/20.500.12870/7736/ESCAP-2025-FS-SDG-Progress-Report.pdf>
- Wright, C. & Nyberg, D. (2024). *Corporations and climate change: An overview*. Retrieved from <https://wires.onlinelibrary.wiley.com/doi/10.1002/wcc.919>